

Eco-efficient manufacturing: Transforming end-of-life wind turbine blade components into floats for PV-floating systems

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Abstract. This study explores the innovative reuse of end-of-life (EoL) wind turbine blade (WTBs) parts as floats for photovoltaic (PV)-floating systems. In response to the growing concerns about EoL WTB waste, this study applies circular economy principles to repurpose high-value composite materials. By transforming a segment of an Enercon E40 WTB into a float for a PV-floating system, this study not only provides a sustainable solution to EoL composites, but also contributes to the development of renewable energy. The article describes the design of the PV-floating system and the lessons learned from its construction. It also provides an outlook on how such a system can be further scaled up.

Keywords. End-of-life wind turbine blades, Circular Economy, Reuse, Repurpose, Composite materials manufacturing, Photovoltaic floating systems

1 Introduction

The rapid expansion of wind energy has led to an increase in wind turbine installations worldwide [1]. This growth, driven by the increasing demand for renewable energy sources, has resulted in significant environmental and logistical challenges, particularly in the management of end-of-life (EoL) wind turbine blades (WTBs). These WTBs are predominantly manufactured from fibre-reinforced thermoset composites, which offer a combination of high specific strength at reasonable costs [2, 3]. Lahuerta *et al.* [4] estimated that over 7.6 million tonnes of EoL WTB composite material mass will need to be decommissioned in Europe by 2050. The use of thermosets poses a significant challenge to the recycling of fibre and polymer systems, which is recognised as a major issue. There is a lack of sustainable and economically viable recycling solutions for composite materials in

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industrial applications [5]. Traditional disposal methods, such as landfill or incineration, pose environmental hazards, highlighting the need for alternative waste management practices.

The concept of a circular economy [6] offers a promising framework to address this issue, emphasising the need to extend the life cycle of material resources. The repurposing of high quality composites from EoL WTBs is a viable strategy with environmental, economic and social benefits [7, 8]. This entails the incorporation of composite components into new products with different functionalities [6]. Some approaches to the repurposing of EoL WTB parts are transmission poles [9], components for bridges [10] or tiny houses [11]. The Rewind-Network also has presented several theoretical concepts for photovoltaic (PV)-floating systems using EoL WTB components as floats [12]. A PV-floating system uses solar panels mounted on floating platforms to generate electricity on bodies of water such as lakes and oceans. Key components of these systems include floats, support structures and solar panels. The system must be designed to stay afloat and stable on the water [13].

This paper presents the design and manufacturing process of a PV-floating system using an EoL WTB segment as a floating body, demonstrating the practical application of the so-called R⁶ strategy [14] in repurposing EoL composites. The R⁶ strategy, which serves as the strategic framework for the European-funded EuReComp project and includes reuse, repair, refurbish, remanufacture, repurpose, and recycle, aims to integrate EoL composite materials back into the economy, minimise waste and promote sustainability.

2 Materials and Methods

The methodological approach focuses on maintaining the structural integrity and the mechanical properties of the original WTB composite material on the highest possible level while repurposing it for a new, environmentally beneficial application.

2.1 EoL WTB segment from an Enercon E40 WTB as a float

The structure used in this work is a segment of an Enercon E40 WTB [15], known for its robust composite design. To separate the E40 WTB segment from the whole E40 WTB, two cuts were made with a wire saw in the area shown in Figure 1.

The segment, weighing 53 kg, has a maximum length of 1,920 mm, a width of 1,130 mm, and a height of 200 mm. The cross-section of the WTB segment varies along its length. These dimensions were chosen based on the buoyancy requirements and the size compatibility with standard solar panels. The WTBs composite material, primarily glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP), provides the required durability and lightweight characteristics ideal for aquatic applications.

Fig. 1. Segment of the EoL E40 WTB used as float

2.2 Repurposed Design: WTB segment as float in a PV-floating system

The PV-floating system is designed with three main components. Firstly, an EoL WTB segment with closed sides using polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) plates (Figure 2), which acts as a float, forming the base of the structure and providing essential buoyancy and stability

in the water. On top of this is a support structure made from lightweight, corrosion resistant materials, which securely holds the solar panel. Finally, a standard PV solar panel is mounted on this support structure, optimally positioned to capture maximum sunlight and generate electricity efficiently.

Fig. 2. Design of the PV-floating system

The integration of these components was guided by principles of sustainable design, with a focus on minimising changes to the original WTB segment to maintain the structural integrity and reduce additional resource consumption.

2.3 Required manufacturing steps to ensure floatability

To adapt the WTB segment for its new role as a float in a PV-floating system, the following manufacturing steps must be carried out.

The *first step* is to thoroughly *clean* the WTB segment to remove any surface contaminants that may have accumulated during its service life. This ensures that subsequent treatments will adhere properly. After cleaning, a *surface treatment* is required to improve adhesion properties, involving mechanical or chemical processes to roughen the surface for better adhesion to subsequent coatings. The *second step* is to create strong *connection points* between the WTB segment and the support structure. To achieve this, the lower profiles of the support structure are attached to the WTB segment with fasteners that can withstand the dynamic loads of the water environment. The *third step* is to completely *seal and close* all exposed areas of the WTB segment. The open sides of the cut WTB segment could be closed with a polymethylmethacrylate plate for example. The durability of the float depends on the use of high-quality marine grade adhesives and sealants that are resistant to water, UV and other environmental factors. Finally, the *fourth step* is to *assemble the support structure and solar panel* to the WTB segment using the established connection points. This step must allow for flexibility in the alignment and adjustment of the solar panel, which is essential to compensate for the uneven mass distribution of the WTB segment. Correct alignment is

crucial to prevent the system from tilting or capsizing due to off-centre buoyancy forces, thereby ensuring the stability and efficiency of the PV-floating system.

3 Results and Discussion

After carrying out the required manufacturing steps (Figure 3a), the result of the PV-floating system during the floatability test is shown in Figure 3b.

Fig. 3. (a) Manufacturing process; (b) Functionality test of the PV-floating system

The adaptation of an EoL WTB segment for use as a float in a PV-floating system showed promising results, demonstrating both the functional viability and environmental benefits of repurposing EoL composite materials.

The modified WTB segment exhibited excellent floatability and stability under typical PV-floating system loading conditions, carrying the weight of the solar panel and its support structure without compromising buoyancy. The adaptability of the support structure and the solar panel on the float can compensate for the uneven mass distribution of the WTB segment. Such a system is therefore also suitable for the problem of the large variety of models and geometries of EoL WTBs. Different types of WTB segments with different geometric shapes can be used for the introduced repurposed application.

A preliminary Life Cycle Assessment showed a significant reduction in environmental impact compared to using virgin materials for similar purposes. By reusing an existing composite, the repurposed application avoids the emissions and waste associated with the production of virgin materials, suggesting that the carbon footprint of the PV-floating system could be reduced compared to systems using entirely new materials [16].

3.1 Challenges and limitations

Some of the challenges in reusing EoL materials for new applications are worth mentioning: Ensuring long-term durability in aquatic environments requires extensive testing and optimisation of sealing methods. The properties of the composite material used in the WTBs demand customised solutions for attaching the support structure, making the design and manufacturing process complex.

In addition, the repurposing of WTB segments as floats needs a particular challenge to be solved: the verification of the safety of the system in accordance with the mechanical requirements. The structural integrity and load carrying capacity of the WTB segment must be verified through experimental investigations to ensure that it meets the required safety standards for PV-floating systems especially for ocean applications. Within this design process, the degraded properties of the composites, which may be caused by their previous use as WTBs, must be carefully assessed and considered. This statement is particularly valid for repurposing composites within any safety-relevant structure. This degradation could affect the strength and durability of the material, which are potentially critical to the long-term performance and safety of the PV-floating system. A detailed assessment of the material condition and the implementation of targeted reinforcements to restore or improve the functional properties is therefore essential.

3.2 Future work

The promising outcomes derived from the presented PV-floating system using an EoL WTB segment, form the basis for further research and development work. A key objective is to upscale the system to accommodate multiple solar panels effectively. Therefore, the manufacturing of a larger PV-floating system supporting four solar panels using two 5 m long EoL WTB segments is proposed. Also, the solar panel support structure of the presented PV-floating system is made of aluminium profiles. To further increase the circularity and the amount of EoL WTB material reused, the possibility of replacing the supporting metallic structure with segments of GFRP spar caps, also coming from EoL WTBs, will be investigated. An initial design can be found in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Design of the PV-floating system on a larger scale

The large-scale construction of the PV-floating system aims to demonstrate the possibility of a repurposed application that contains a significant amount of EoL WTB composites and can be efficiently mass produced for a specific end market. To ensure that the PV-floating system contains a high amount of composite material, multiple units will be connected to form an even larger system. Such an extension will allow the feasibility and efficiency to be tested in real-world conditions.

In addition to scaling up, it is imperative that extensive durability studies are carried out on the repurposed composites. These studies should monitor the effects of weathering [17], “water-specific” dynamic loading (waves etc.), biofouling and degradation of mechanical properties over time (ageing) and provide important data on long-term viability in aquatic environments.

In parallel, manufacturing processes need to be refined to improve efficiency and reduce costs, possibly by automating certain production steps and adopting more sustainable sealing and joining techniques. According to the work of Henao *et al.* [18], who investigated the life cycle costs of repurposing EoL WTB as transmission poles, economic analysis is needed to understand the regulatory, market, and financial barriers to the commercial adoption of such PV-floating systems from EoL WTB segment floats. Also, a sustainable business guide (SBG) assisted by Artificial Intelligence (AI) to support decision-making could be a feasible approach to take business opportunities to the next level [19]. In this sense, the design and manufacturing process of PV-floating systems should be accompanied by an SBG that integrates the entire value chain and brings all stakeholders together to conduct a sustainable solution to the market. The SBG will first consider collecting data related to the inspection and analysis of WTB [20]. Next, it will incorporate technical thresholds referring to European construction standards [21]. Following this, through the development of an AI-assisted Decision System, the SBG will be capable of predicting the optimal route for the reuse or repair of EoL WTB, considering economic, environmental, and technical factors [22]. Subsequently, through an analysis of Porter's five forces [23-25], the SBG will explore substitute products, main competitors, customers, and suppliers. Finally, the SBG will integrate several circular EoL WTB alternatives, including their validation in the floating photovoltaic systems proposed in this work. These analyses will help to identify the necessary incentives or support mechanisms to encourage wider adoption.

4 Conclusion

This study demonstrates the feasibility and the environmental benefits of repurposing EoL WTB segments as floating structures for PV systems. In line with circular economy principles, this innovative approach not only addresses the pressing issue of composite waste management, but also contributes to the development of a sustainable, low-impact renewable energy infrastructure. The results of this project pave the way for future applications where EoL composites can be effectively reused to improve sustainability and resource efficiency in various other industries. As such, this research offers a promising outlook for the sustainable EoL management of composites and suggests that, with further development and scaling up, reused materials can play a key role in the transition to a more sustainable and resilient energy future.

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